

Raman scattering investigation of stoichiometric and off-stoichiometric Bi₂Te₃ thin films prepared by e-beam evaporation technique

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Abstract

The composition–influenced structural aspects in Bi₂Te₃ thin films significantly influence the thermoelectric properties. E-beam evaporated Bi₂Te₃ thin films and their thermoelectric properties are scarcely explored. Here, we present the Raman spectral investigations on the stoichiometric and off-stoichiometric (Bi-rich and Te-rich) e-beam evaporated nanocrystalline Bi₂Te₃ thin films. Room temperature deposited thin films (BT-AD) are vacuum annealed (BT-VA) at a pressure of 3×10^{-6} mbar and at temperature ranging from 100 °C to 300 °C. The local structural details of the BT-AD and BT-VA films were investigated by Raman spectroscopy using 488 nm laser. The Raman spectra show the infrared (IR) active optical phonon mode (A_{1u}) is greatly activated. This mode is Raman forbidden in bulk crystals due to its inversion symmetry. Blue shift for A_{1g}^2 and A_{1u} modes for annealing temperatures up to 150 °C, further indicates that the atoms (Bi and (Te) vibrate perpendicular to the layered surface. This could happen mainly due to thinner layers of films. These observations from Raman spectra are correlated to compositional, morphological and crystallite size analysis of BT-AD and BT-VA films using a detailed XRD, FESEM and HRTEM measurements, together with the prediction from the group theory. We attribute the appearance of infrared active (A_{1u}) Raman spectrum to crystal symmetry breaking of Bi₂Te₃ crystallites in the films. E-beam evaporated thin films and subsequent annealing process provide substantial variable parameters to tailor the structure and composition that will find potential application in thermoelectric devices.

Keywords

Bi₂Te₃ thin films, e-beam, thermoelectric materials.